

MONASH
University

Ethereum Foundation 2025 Academic Grants Round

Research Proposal

Title

Bridging Islamic Finance and Blockchain: Tokenizing Green Sukuk on Ethereum for Sustainable and Inclusive DeFi

Project Abstract

The integration of Islamic finance with Ethereum's decentralized finance (DeFi) ecosystem remains underexplored, despite shared principles such as transparency, trust, and asset-backed transactions—whether through real assets in Islamic finance or tokenization in blockchain. This project addresses this gap by examining the tokenization of Green Sukuk (Islamic green bonds) in Malaysia, a global leader in Islamic finance. By analyzing Malaysia's economic development and sustainable Islamic financing, we aim to identify regulatory, technical, and market challenges while deriving insights for Ethereum's DeFi ecosystem. Our research will provide theoretical contributions and policy recommendations to enhance financial inclusion, ethical investment, and sustainability on Ethereum.

Objectives

This project aims to formulate recommendations for enhancing the adoption, fairness, and resilience of the Ethereum ecosystem through a qualitative analysis of Malaysia's economic development. Our foundational hypothesis posits that insightful parallels can be drawn between development economics and blockchain economics, particularly between Malaysia's economic trajectory since 1957 and Ethereum's evolution. Over nearly seven decades since attaining independence from British colonial rule, Malaysia has demonstrated remarkable progress in various measurable indicators, including GDP per capita, industrialization, economic diversification, trade, poverty reduction, and infrastructure development. While numerous factors have contributed to Malaysia's economic growth, our study will underscore the pivotal role of Islamic finance.

Islamic finance has significantly contributed to economic development, especially in Muslim-majority countries, as documented in numerous books and scholarly articles. For instance, the book *Economic Development and Islamic Finance* (World Bank, 2013) illustrates how principles like risk-sharing and ethical investment align with

development economics goals by fostering financial inclusion and economic stability. It underscores that Islamic finance can tackle socio-economic challenges in these regions by offering interest-free financial services and supports sustainable development through investments in real assets and socially responsible projects. Recent findings by Hanif et al. (2024), based on an analysis of 15 countries over the period 2001–2020, indicate that the Islamic financial services industry positively contributes to economic growth in the sampled countries, as evidenced by multiple regression analyses.

In Malaysia, Islamic finance has emerged as a significant component of the overall financial system, reflecting the country's commitment to integrating Shariah-compliant financial practices. According to the latest *Global Islamic Finance Report* (Cambridge Institute of Islamic Finance, 2024), Malaysia's Islamic financial system, with assets valued at USD 230 billion, ranks third globally, following Saudi Arabia (USD 850 billion) and the United Arab Emirates (USD 260 billion). Furthermore, Malaysia is the leading nation in Sukuk issuance, holding a market share of 52%. Sukuk are Islamic bonds that generate returns based on the performance of underlying assets rather than interest. As reported by the World Bank (Bennett & Coyle, 2025), the total issuance of Sukuk in 2024 reached approximately USD 180 billion. The primary jurisdictions contributing to this issuance were Malaysia, Saudi Arabia, and Indonesia.

Green Sukuk are Shariah-compliant financial instruments specifically designed to fund environmentally sustainable projects, such as renewable energy and climate resilience initiatives. They function similarly to conventional Sukuk. In July 2017 Malaysia issued the inaugural Green Sukuk under its [Sustainable and Responsible Investment \(SRI\)](#) scheme, successfully raising RM 250 million to finance a large-scale solar power project. By integrating Islamic finance principles with environmental objectives, Green Sukuk provide a unique mechanism for promoting sustainable development within the framework of ethical investment. These “Islamic green bonds,” as they are sometimes referred to, have expanded to constitute approximately 10% of the total Sukuk market (Bennett & Coyle, 2025).

While the contributions of Islamic finance to sustainable economic development in Southeast Asia and other regions are well understood and documented, the intersection of Islamic finance and blockchain technology has received relatively less scholarly attention. For instance, a recent systematic review by Čiković and Keček (2025) highlights a significant literature gap and a paucity of scientific findings concerning emerging financial technologies, particularly within the context of Islamic banking. This dearth of research is surprising, given the several shared principles between Islamic finance and blockchain-based decentralized finance that warrant further exploration. Notably, both Islamic and decentralized finance emphasize trust and transparency, aim to reduce reliance on intermediaries, and promote a shared communal ethos and responsibility. Furthermore, Islamic finance mandates that

financial transactions be backed by tangible assets or services, which is conceptually well aligned with the topic of tokenization of real world assets on the blockchain.

Our project aims to address the need for theoretical clarity and practical progress at the intersection of Islamic and decentralized finance by focusing on the tokenization of Green Sukuk in Malaysia. Through semi-structured interviews and an in-depth review of the extant literature (see below for more details on the methodology), we seek to make a significant theoretical contribution to the academic literature. Additionally, we aim to formulate policy recommendations for the Ethereum platform itself.

Outcomes: *How This Project Benefits the Ethereum Ecosystem*

This project contributes to the Ethereum ecosystem by offering insights from Malaysia's economic development and Islamic finance to enhance the adoption, fairness, and resilience of blockchain economies. Specifically, this project has the potential to significantly benefit the broader Ethereum ecosystem in two ways, both of which align with the Ethereum Foundation's [Wishlist](#) as follows:

1. Development Economics and Blockchain Economics

- By drawing parallels between Malaysia's economic growth and Ethereum's evolution, this study provides a new lens for understanding blockchain ecosystems as emerging economies.
- The role of Islamic finance—emphasizing trust, transparency, and risk-sharing—offers a compelling case for improving decentralized financial (DeFi) mechanisms on Ethereum.

2. Expanding Historical Contexts

- The project broadens Ethereum's historical perspectives by integrating Islamic finance, a system deeply rooted in non-Western economic thought.
- The study of Green Sukuk tokenization introduces a novel approach to sustainable finance on Ethereum, paving the way for ethically-aligned, asset-backed blockchain instruments.

By bridging Islamic finance principles with decentralized finance, this project provides both theoretical contributions and actionable policy recommendations, ultimately fostering a more inclusive, equitable, and resilient Ethereum ecosystem.

Grant Scope

This project explores the intersection of development economics, Islamic finance, and blockchain technology, focusing on the tokenization of Green Sukuk on Ethereum. By analyzing Malaysia's economic transformation and the role of Islamic

finance, we will assess how Ethereum's DeFi infrastructure can enhance financial inclusion and sustainability.

Key Research Areas

- Economic Parallels: Lessons from Malaysia's growth trajectory applied to Ethereum's evolving blockchain economy.
- Islamic Finance and Blockchain: Aligning Shariah-compliant finance with Ethereum's decentralized ecosystem.
- Tokenized Green Sukuk: Feasibility, regulatory challenges, and adoption barriers for fractional Sukuk investments.
- Stakeholder Insights: Interviews with regulators, financial institutions, blockchain developers, and investors.

Expected Outputs

- Research Report: A comprehensive study detailing insights from Malaysia's economic model, the role of Islamic finance, and the feasibility of Green Sukuk tokenization on Ethereum.
- Policy Recommendations: Insightful recommendations for Ethereum developers and policymakers to enhance blockchain-based Islamic finance applications.
- Academic Contribution: Submission of findings to peer-reviewed open-access journals and conference presentations.
- Industry White Paper: Practical insights for Ethereum-based DeFi projects exploring Shariah-compliant financial instruments.

This project will offer valuable insights for integrating Islamic finance principles into Ethereum's DeFi ecosystem, ultimately fostering a more inclusive, transparent, and sustainable blockchain economy.

Related Work

Existing research most relevant to this project

Bennett, M., & Coyle, H. (2025, March 4). State of the Sukuk market and prospects for growth. World Bank Blogs.

<https://blogs.worldbank.org/en/allaboutfinance/state-of-the-sukuk-market-and-prospects-for-growth>

Cambridge Institute of Islamic Finance. (2024). *Global Islamic Finance Report 2024*. London, United Kingdom.

Čiković, K. F., & Keček, D. (2025). The application of blockchain technology in Islamic banking literature: A PRISMA-compliant literature review. In H. Abazi-Alili, A.

Bexheti, V. Ramadani, C. Leal, & C. Peixeira Marques (Eds.), *Navigating economic uncertainty – Vol. 2. ISCBE 2024. Springer proceedings in business and economics* (pp. 21-38). Springer, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-73510-3_2

Delle Foglie, A., Panetta, I. C., Boukrami, E., & Vento, G. (2021). The impact of the Blockchain technology on the global Sukuk industry: smart contracts and asset tokenisation. *Technology Analysis & Strategic Management*, 37(4), 417–431. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09537325.2021.1939000>

Hanif, M., Chaker, M., & Sabah, A. (2024). Islamic finance and economic growth: Global evidence. *Digest of Middle East Studies*, 33(1), 83–102. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dome.12313>

Iqbal, Z., & Mirakhor, A. (Eds.). (2013). *Economic development and Islamic finance*. Washington, DC: World Bank. <https://doi.org/10.1596/978-0-8213-9953-8>

Khan, N., Kchouri, B., Yattoo, N. A., Kräussl, Z., Patel, A., & State, R. (2022). Tokenization of sukuk: Ethereum case study. *Global Finance Journal*, 51, 100539-. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.gfj.2020.100539>

Redzuan, H. (2024, September 2). *Halal Crypto: Could blockchain be a boost for Shariah-compliant finance?* King's College London. <https://www.kcl.ac.uk/news/halal-crypto-could-blockchain-be-a-boost-for-shariah-compliant-finance>

Taghizadeh-Hesary, F., Thas Thaker, H. M., Bhatti, M. I., & Mohd Thas Thaker, M. A. (2025). *Islamic Finance and Sustainability: A Research Companion*. 1st ed. Taylor & Francis Group. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003518617>

Specific gap this research is addressing within this context

Despite Malaysia's leadership in Green Sukuk issuance and its well-established Islamic finance framework, there is a significant gap in research on the fractional tokenization of Green Sukuk using Ethereum blockchain technology. While traditional Green Sukuk provides sustainable financing for environmentally friendly projects, its liquidity challenges, high issuance costs, regulatory uncertainties, and Shariah compliance considerations remain largely unexplored in the context of Ethereum-based tokenization and decentralized finance (DeFi) solutions. This study seeks to examine how Ethereum's smart contract capabilities, security token standards (ERC-1400), and decentralized exchanges (DEXs) like Uniswap can facilitate a compliant and efficient Green Sukuk marketplace.

Technically, the Ethereum blockchain enables the fractionalization of Green Sukuk, allowing retail and institutional investors to participate in sustainable finance projects through ERC-1400 or ERC-20 security tokens. However, the regulatory status of

trading platforms such as Uniswap and centralized exchanges like Luno in Malaysia remains uncertain, as cryptocurrency-based transactions are restricted for security token trading. The conversion of ETH into stablecoins (such as USDT or MYR-pegged stablecoins) before exchanging for MYR presents additional compliance risks to both investors and issuers, particularly regarding anti-money laundering (AML) and securities regulations. Furthermore, the complexity of smart contract development for Shariah-compliant Green Sukuk is a major challenge. These contracts must incorporate Islamic finance principles such as profit-sharing (Mudarabah), leasing (Ijarah), and risk-sharing mechanisms while ensuring transparency and avoidance of Riba (interest) and Gharar (excessive uncertainty).

Another critical issue is the absence of a structured framework for digital securities, security token offerings (STOs), and secondary market liquidity for tokenized Sukuk in Malaysia. Although Ethereum-based tokenization provides transparency, immutability, and automated enforcement of contracts, the lack of clear regulatory support limits its adoption. The extant literature as detailed below has not comprehensively analyzed these technical, regulatory, and Shariah compliance challenges, nor has it engaged with all relevant stakeholders, including Ethereum blockchain developers, regulators, issuers, investors, Islamic fintech innovators, ESG policymakers, and Shariah scholars. For example, Čiković, K. F., & Keček, D. (2025) conducted A PRISMA-compliant literature review on the application of blockchain technologies and identified around 13 recent studies. However, to the best of our judgment, none of these studies specifically examined fractional Green Sukuk, particularly in relation to ESG factors, financial inclusion, blockchain integration, and smart contracts technicality. Most existing research focuses on the theory of diffusion of innovations and the adoption, primarily offering regulatory recommendations rather than exploring how blockchain technology, smart contracts, and ESG principles can be integrated into Sukuk tokenization to enhance transparency, efficiency, and inclusivity. Other literature provide insights to the Sukuk market and prospects (i.e., Bennett & Coyle , 2025; Cambridge Institute of Islamic Finance, 2024). This study aims to fill that gap by conducting qualitative interviews to explore the viability, risks, and solutions for tokenized fractional Green Sukuk on Ethereum in Malaysia as a leading global issuer of Green sukuk, contributing to the broader conversation on blockchain adoption in Islamic finance.

Project Team

The research team comprises:

1. Dr. Mohammed Sharaf Shaiban (Principal Investigator), Department of Finance, School of Business, Monash University Malaysia
2. Professor Andreas Deppeler (Collaborator), Department of Finance, School of Business, Monash University Malaysia
3. Research Assistant (TBD)

Estimated Research Hours per Month (Hours/Month)

Name	Role	Estimated Hours/Month
Dr. Mohammed Sharaf Shaiban	Principal Investigator	15-20 hours
Professor Andreas Deppeler	Collaborator	10-15 hours
Research Assistant (TBD)	Supporting literature review, data collection, and analysis	10-12 hours

Breakdown of Effort

- **Dr. Mohammed Sharaf Shaiban (Principal Investigator)**
 - Monash ethical clearance, documentation and approvals
 - Leading research design and execution
 - Conducting interviews with key stakeholders
 - Overseeing qualitative data analysis
 - Writing the research report and policy recommendations
 - Presenting findings at conferences
- **Professor Andreas Deppeler (Collaborator)**
 - Advising on blockchain technology and DeFi integration
 - Assisting in interview structuring and stakeholder engagement
 - Conducting interviews with stakeholders
 - Reviewing the research report and contributing to analysis
 - Providing insights into Ethereum and fintech applications
- **Research Assistant**
 - Conducting literature reviews and secondary data collection
 - Assisting in interview transcriptions and qualitative analysis
 - Supporting report writing and preparing materials for conferences

These hours will vary slightly depending on the project phase, with more intensive work expected during data collection and analysis months.

Background

Dr. Mohammed Sharaf Shaiban is a Senior Lecturer at Monash University Malaysia, where he has been a faculty member since 2011. He brings extensive industry and academic experience, with a strong background in accounting and finance. A certified Public Accountant, has been a member of the American Accounting Association and permanent member the Malaysian Finance Association.

Throughout his career, Dr. Shaiban has held leadership positions in both government and private sectors, contributing to his diverse expertise. His research focuses on stock price informativeness, sustainability, and banking, with publications in esteemed academic journals and active participation in international conferences. Dr.

Shaiban has been a principal investigator for FRGS grants and Monash internal grants.

He has been awarded research grants from institutions such as the Malaysian Ministry of Higher Education and the Malaysian Banking Institute. His current work is centered on Fintech entrepreneurship and startups in emerging markets, reflecting his commitment to innovation in the financial technology sector.

Dr. Shaiban holds an MBA in Accounting from the University of Denver, USA, and a PhD from the University of Malaya, Malaysia.

Related academic and engagement work

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/mohamed-shaiban-71b9a288/>

ResearchGate: <https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Mohammed-Shaiban>

Google Scholar: https://scholar.google.com/citations?user=_nXu30kAAAAJ&hl=en

Monash Profile: <https://research.monash.edu/en/persons/mohammed-shaiban>

Dr. Andreas Deppeler is a Professor of Practice in Financial Technology (Fintech) at Monash University Malaysia. His research interests encompass corporate strategy and the governance of emerging technologies, particularly decentralized finance and artificial intelligence (AI).

Before returning to academia as a teacher and researcher, Dr. Deppeler accumulated nearly two decades of experience in the corporate sector across Europe, the United States, and Asia. He was a management consultant at BCG, a global strategy consulting firm, held various project management and line management roles at a major Swiss bank, and ran his own consulting firm.

Originally from Switzerland, Dr. Deppeler has been living and working in Southeast Asia since 2016. Prior to his current role at Monash University, he was an adjunct associate professor at NUS Business School in Singapore and a Director of Data and Analytics at PwC Singapore. At PwC, he played a key role in acquiring and leading a portfolio of client engagements in data governance, AI, and blockchain.

Dr. Deppeler holds an MSc in Theoretical Physics from ETH Zurich, a PhD in Theoretical Physics from Rutgers University, and is a CFA Charterholder.

Related academic and engagement work

LinkedIn: <https://www.linkedin.com/in/andreasdeppeler/>

Monash Profile: <https://research.monash.edu/en/persons/andreas-deppeler>

Methodology

Selection of Interview Participants

This study will adopt a structured approach to identifying and recruiting interview participants to ensure a well-rounded and comprehensive analysis. A total of 24 to 33 interviews will be conducted with a benchmark of 20 participants, targeting key stakeholders involved in Ethereum-based blockchain applications and Green Sukuk issuance in Malaysia. The selection process will focus on decision-makers, practitioners, and technical experts from various sectors to capture diverse perspectives. The stakeholder groups and their respective recommended number of interviews are as follows.

Policymakers and Regulators (4–6 interviews): Representatives from Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM), the Securities Commission Malaysia (SC), Labuan Financial Services Authority (Labuan FSA), Malaysia Digital Economy Corporation (MDEC), and the Ministry of Finance (MoF) will provide insights into regulatory considerations and the feasibility of integrating blockchain into Green Sukuk investments and Islamic finance in general.

Green Sukuk Issuers & Islamic Finance Institutions (4–6 interviews): This group includes Sukuk-issuing banks (e.g., Cagamas Berhad, CIMB), Islamic financial institutions, and sustainability-focused investment bodies (i.e., Malaysian Green Technology and Climate Change Corporation (MGTC)) to assess the demand, structuring, and compliance aspects of blockchain-based Green Sukuk.

Ethereum-Based Blockchain Players (4–5 interviews): Interviews will be conducted with representatives from licensed crypto exchanges (such as Luno, Tokenize Xchange, and MX Global), blockchain developers, and the Blockchain Association Malaysia to evaluate technical implementation and industry readiness.

Startups and Fintech Companies (3–4 interviews): Insights from Islamic fintech startups, crowdfunding platforms, and tokenization service providers will help understand the role of blockchain in expanding access to Green Sukuk investments.

Academics and Shariah Scholars (3–4 interviews): Experts from pioneer Islamic research institutions such International Centre for Education in Islamic Finance (INCEIF), University of Malaya (UM), and Shariah advisory bodies (e.g., members of the Shariah Advisory Council, BNM & SC) will contribute to ensuring the project aligns with Islamic financial principles and sustainability standards.

Users and Potential Fractional Investors (6–8 interviews): This category includes retail investors, high-net-worth individuals, and participants in Ethereum-based token platforms who are potential adopters of fractional Green Sukuk investments. Their perspectives will provide valuable insights into investor sentiment, adoption challenges, and market demand.

Participants will be recruited through a combination of snowball sampling, referrals, and professional networks to ensure access to relevant industry experts and users. This targeted approach will provide a balanced, in-depth understanding of the potential for Ethereum-based fractional investment in Green Sukuk in Malaysia.

Primary Data Collection: Expert Interviews

The primary data will be gathered through semi-structured expert interviews with key stakeholders involved in Ethereum-based blockchain applications and Islamic finance. An interview guide will be developed based on existing literature and industry best practices to ensure flexibility, depth of insights and structured discussions. The interviews will provide qualitative insights into the potential benefits, risks, and regulatory implications of tokenizing Green Sukuk on Ethereum. The data collected will be analyzed to identify the main opportunities and challenges in implementing blockchain-based fractional Sukuk investments in Malaysia.

Secondary Data Collection: Document Review

To complement the primary data, secondary data will be collected through a comprehensive document review. This will include policy reports, regulatory guidelines, industry white papers, financial institution reports, company websites, and official statistics. The documents will be sourced from regulatory bodies such as Bank Negara Malaysia (BNM) and the Securities Commission (SC), financial institutions, and blockchain industry reports. This secondary data will help validate the findings from expert interviews and provide a broader industry context.

Research Approach: Grounded Theory and Qualitative Analysis

The study follows a Grounded Theory approach (Glaser & Strauss, 1967), where data will be systematically collected and analyzed to develop a conceptual framework identifying the key drivers and barriers of using Ethereum for fractional investment in Green Sukuk and Islamic finance in general. This methodology is suitable for discovering new relationships, explaining emerging trends, and generating theoretical insights on the integration of blockchain technology into Islamic finance.

A constructivist qualitative research paradigm (Creswell, 2018) will be applied, focusing on how the complexities of the sociocultural and regulatory environment influence the adoption of Ethereum-based Green Sukuk investments. The study aims to uncover multiple perspectives from blockchain developers, financial institutions, Shariah scholars, and investors, contributing to a deeper understanding of the practical, economic, and regulatory factors shaping blockchain adoption in Malaysia's Islamic finance sector.

Timeline

This study on using Ethereum (DeFi) for fractional investment in Green Sukuk in Malaysia will be conducted over 12 months, progressing through key phases: ethics approval, participant recruitment, data collection, analysis, and dissemination of findings. The project will begin with securing research ethics approval from Monash, ensuring compliance with the university ethical research standards. Concurrently, participant recruitment will take place using snowball sampling, referrals, and professional networks to engage regulators, Green Sukuk issuers, blockchain developers, financial institutions, Shariah scholars, and potential investors.

The data collection phase will involve semi-structured interviews with different stakeholders and could also include additional focus group discussions with potential investors. The interviews aim to examine the opportunities, challenges, and regulatory implications of Ethereum-based fractional Sukuk investments. This will be followed by transcription and systematic qualitative analysis to identify key themes related to market feasibility, adoption specifically by potential investors and Green Sukuk issuers, challenges, and regulatory considerations.

Findings will then be compiled into a comprehensive research report, refined through internal reviews, and prepared for dissemination. The project will conclude with conference presentations (subject to scheduling) and submission for publication in a peer-reviewed open-access journals, contributing to the broader discourse on blockchain applications in Islamic finance and sustainable investments

Timeline and Budget Allocation

Milestone	Months	Budget	No of Hours	Summary of Work & Subtasks
1. Research Ethics Application	2	N/A	10	Prepare and submit ethics application, obtain approval (principal investigator/ no hourly charge)
2. Participant Recruitment	2-3	\$343	57	Identify and contact key stakeholders, send invitations, schedule interviews. TA cost (24 hours x \$14.30). No charge for hourly work by principal and collaborator
3. Conduct Interviews and Focus Group Discussions	4-5	\$4515	141	Conduct qualitative interviews, organize focus group sessions. TA cost (36 hours x \$14.30)+ per diem (\$ 1500), local transport (\$1000)and participants tokens (\$1500). No charge for hourly work by principal and collaborator
4. Transcribe Interview Data	6-7	\$2144	45	Transcribe and verify interview recordings for accuracy (30x\$50) + TA verification and compiling (30 x1.5 hours x \$14.30)

5. Analysis and Results	7-8	N/A	70	Thematic analysis of data, identification of key insights and trends. No charge for hourly work by principal and collaborator
6. Write Report	8-11	N/AX	40	Draft research findings, integrate literature review, prepare recommendations (including 12 hours TA x 14.30) and 40 hour by principal . No charge for hourly work by principal and collaborator
7. Synthesis and Review	9-11	N/A	35	Peer review, final revisions, submission of the final report
8. Conference Presentation (Subject to Conf. Schedule)	12	\$6986	44	Prepare and deliver presentation at relevant academic conference including travelling time (32 hours principal + 34 hours TA time) @ cost (\$2500 submission + \$ 4000 Conference fees and travel + 34 TA work for preparing submission documents and conference materials)
Total		14000	440 - 560	

Budget

The grant will be used to cover the research expenses listed below.

Item	Description	US\$
Principal Researchers Costs	Costs associated with presenting findings at a relevant conference, including registration, travel, and accommodation (publication cost)	4,000
Data collection costs	Data collection cost (30 participants- Tokens of participants)	1,500
	Local transport to interview participants and collect data	1,500
	Per diem	1,000
	Fees for submitting findings to open-access journals	2500
	Research Assistant costs (140 hours).Support for literature review, secondary data collection, and analysis.	2000
Software cost	Software cost (transcription for 30 scripts)	1,500
Total requested amount		14,000

